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Abstract:

This deliverable is a report on SSHOC metadata and data interoperability problems. It pertains to Task 3.5 under responsibility of CESSDA/FSD. In addition to an inventory of data and metadata interoperability problems, this deliverable includes choices for SSHOC recommended formats and priorities for providing conversion services and planning solutions.

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
CLARIN-ERIC	Daan Broeder	daan.broeder@di.huc.knaw.nl
EKUT	Thorsten Trippel	thorsten.trippel@uni-tuebingen.de
E-RIHS/CNR	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	emiliano.deglinnocenti@cnr.it
CNR	Roberta Giacomi	roberta.giacomi@gmail.com
CNR	Maurizio Sanesi	maurizio.sanesi.eng@gmail.com
CESSDA/FSD	Mari Kleemola	mari.kleemola@tuni.fi
CESSDA/FSD	Katja Moilanen	katja.moilanen@tuni.fi
CESSDA/FSD	Henri Ala-Lahti	henri.ala-lahti@tuni.fi
CESSDA/SND	Caspar Jordan	caspar.jordan@snd.gu.se
CESSDA/SND	Iris Alfredsson	iris.alfredsson@snd.gu.se
CESSDA/UKDS	Hervé L'Hours	herve@essex.ac.uk
ÖAW	Matej Ďurčo	matej.durco@oeaw.ac.at

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Executive Summary

The SSHOC project aims to build a Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) as part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by implementing a cloud-based infrastructure. The goal is to provide a recognisable and accessible environment for data, tools, services and trainings, and to maximise data reuse through Open Science and FAIR principles.

In line with these goals, this report provides an inventory of data formats and metadata standards that are currently used and relevant for the research infrastructures currently managed by the SSHOC main stakeholders, recommendations of specific formats and standards for increasing interoperability, and prioritisations for providing conversion services and planning solutions.

In the context of this deliverable, selected experts from the SSHOC stakeholder's infrastructures were interviewed about research data and metadata use in their respective infrastructures. Special attention was paid to interoperability aspects.

The interviews and the desk research indicated both the diversity of the SSHOC communities and the diversity of metadata standards used and needed. Therefore, this deliverable recommends a variety of metadata standards and data formats. The recommended metadata standards include domain specific metadata standards for each domain but also Dublin Core and relaxed DataCite for all domains.

The diversity of SSHOC communities is also shown in their data: there is a large selection of different media types and an enormous selection of data formats. The recommended data formats include a small selection of data formats for some general media types e.g. images, text annotations. The format for controlled vocabularies was also examined and SKOS was selected as the recommended format. It is worth noting that hardly any recommendation can fulfill all the use cases, so other metadata standards, data formats and formats for controlled vocabularies may still be used when necessary.

The priorities for providing conversion services and planning solutions were decided based on the interviews and on the needs from other SSHOC tasks. The challenges and solutions are analysed for each SSHOC community and both the priority and the needed actions are specified. We expect the prioritisation to change in the course of the project with the appearance of new requirements.

Beyond WP3, this document is relevant to WP4, WP5, WP7 and WP9. Ongoing discussion between the work packages and tasks is needed.

The authors of this report wish to thank the interviewed informants for their time and valuable contribution.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ARIADNE	Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe
ARK	Archival Resource Key
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CH	Cultural Heritage
CHAT	Codes for the Human Analysis of Transcripts
CIDOC	Comité International pour la Documentation / ICOM's International Committee for Documentation
CIDOC-CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIAH	Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CLAVAS	CLARIN Vocabulary Service
CMDI	Component Metadata Infrastructure
CMM	CESSDA Metadata Model
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Service
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DASISH	Data Services Infrastructure For the Social Sciences and Humanities
DCDDM	DARIAH Collection Description Data Model
DCMI / DC	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative / Dublin Core
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DOCX	Office Open XML Document
EAD	Encoded Archival Description
EAF	EUDICO/ELAN Annotation File
EDM	Europeana Data Model
EKUT	Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen
ELAN	Eudico Linguistic Annotation
ELSST	European Language Social Science Thesaurus
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUDICO	European Distributed Corpora
EQB	European Question Bank
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESS	European Social Survey

EXMARaLDA	EXtensible Markup Language for Discourse Annotation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FITS	File Information Toolset
FLAC	Free Lossless Audio Codec
FoLiA	Format for Linguistic Annotation
FSD	Finnish Social Science Data Archive
GND	Gemeinsame Normdatei
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
IIF	International Image Interoperability Framework
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JPEG	Joint Photographics Experts Group
MARC	MAchine Readable Cataloguing
METS	Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard
MODS	Metadata Object Description Schema
MPEG	Moving Picture Expert Group
MP4	MPEG-4 Part 14
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLTK	Natural Language ToolKit
NSD	Norwegian Centre for Research Data
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
ODT	Open Document Text
OLAC	Open Language Archives Community
ORE	Object Exchange and Reuse
PaQu	Parse and Query
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
PEM	PARTHENOS Entities Model
PID	Persistent Identifier
PREMIS	Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies
PROV-O	PROV (Provenance) Ontology
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
QuDEx	Qualitative Data Exchange Format
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SAS	Statistical Analysis System
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe

SMM	Scientific Metadata Model
SSHOC	Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud
SSHOCro	SSHOC Reference Ontology
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SND	Swedish National Data Service
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STATA	Statistics and Data
SVG	Scalable Vector Graphics
TADIRAH	Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities
TAR	Tape ARchive
TCF	Text Corpus Format
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
TGN	Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format
TSV	Tab-Separated Values
UKDS	UK Data Service
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
VIAF	Virtual Authority File
WAV	Waveform Audio File Format
X3D	eXtensible 3D Graphics
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
XSLT	eXtensible Stylesheet Language Transformations
ÖAW / OEAW	Austrian Academy of Sciences

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

SSHOC brings together different multidisciplinary communities, traditions and practices from ERICs and projects in the ESFRI Social and Cultural Innovation domain: CESSDA, ESS, SHARE, CLARIN, DARIAH and E-RIHS. In this report, we make recommendations on metadata and data formats to be used in SSHOC. Our aim is very practical: to support the building or the reuse of available tools to convert data or metadata formats from one to another. We base our recommendations in our inventory of metadata and data formats and standards that are currently in use within the SSHOC communities. We do not expect to create a single unified domain of data and metadata, but our recommendations and conversion services can limit the number of data and metadata variants, increasing efficiency for SSH and CH service development. We acknowledge that the vital issue of format conversion exists within a broader context of interoperability issues and challenges; the wider interoperability landscape is addressed briefly in Chapter 6.

This deliverable is due in month six (June 2019) and thus describes the situation in the early stages of the project. Metadata standards and data formats and their use is an area that is constantly developing. Task 3.5 plans to continuously update the inventory during SSHOC project although no further deliverable is planned. Updates will be undertaken in collaboration with other project tasks to further develop interoperable solutions within SSHOC.

1.2 Relation to other SSHOC tasks and outputs

In the SSHOC Description of Action, data, metadata and controlled vocabularies are mentioned in six of the ten work packages. This is to be expected, as they are essential building blocks of distributed research infrastructures. Most of the work packages are relying on existing data formats, metadata standards or controlled vocabularies. However, two tasks are set to produce a novel metadata model: Task 4.7 Modeling the SSHOC data life cycle and Task 7.1 User requirements, Conceptual Model and System Architecture of the SSH Open Marketplace. Descriptions of tasks 4.7, 5.7 and 9.4 refer directly to the outputs of Task 3.5.

Task 3.5 is closely tied to the work of WP7 in developing the SSHOC marketplace, a discovery service aiming to offer solutions, in the sense of descriptions or instructions on how to achieve a certain goal. This includes the identification of tools for various tasks of the research process, which also implies the question of what data types and formats individual tools accept as inputs and deliver as outputs. Thus, task 3.5 and WP7 inform each other reciprocally on which tools are available, which formats they support and which format conversions may be needed to allow the use of a certain tool, given a dataset in a given format. Task 3.5 will also provide relevant data and metadata conversion services that will be offered as part of the SSHOC Switchboard built by task 3.6. It will allow users to invoke specific conversions when encountering specific data-types.

Beyond WP3, this document is relevant to WP4, WP5, WP7 and WP9. Ongoing discussion between the work packages and tasks is needed.

1.3 Background and earlier work

All the ERICs and ESFRI projects involved in SSHOC have worked with metadata, data and interoperability issues before this project. The following is not an exhaustive list but illustrates the previous work.

CESSDA and its Service Providers have been active in developing the DDI metadata standard since the 1990s (DDI Alliance 2015). In 2012-2015, CESSDA and national statistical institutes worked towards preparing a service with higher quality and more usable metadata in the Data without Boundaries project¹.

CLARIN developed the Component Metadata Infrastructure (CMDI), to create an interoperable domain of metadata profiles for Language Resources. This was developed in different national and EU projects and standardised in a series of ISO standards starting with ISO 24622-1:2015.

The DASISH project² in 2012-2014 brought together CLARIN, DARIAH, CESSDA, ESS and SHARE with a goal to determine areas of possible synergies in the infrastructure development. The project analysed and compared the different metadata strategies of CLARIN, DARIAH and CESSDA and concluded that it is “unrealistic to achieve perfect standardisation across all relevant data sources and disciplines” but that it is important to “promote collaboration on metadata profiles within each research community in the SSH area”. (DASISH 2014.)

The ARIADNE project³ compiled a registry of metadata schemas, vocabularies and other standards relevant to the archaeology domain. They chose CIDOC-CRM as the basis of the ARIADNE Reference Model. A suite of extensions was developed to address the complexity of archaeological data integration.⁴

The PARTHENOS⁵ project (2014-2019) has built an infrastructure whose objective is to strengthen the cohesion of research across a number of related fields associated with the humanities, including linguistic studies, cultural heritage, history and archaeology. Existing research infrastructure such as the aforementioned ARIADNE, as well as ESFRI landmarks like CLARIN and DARIAH, and projects, such as E-RIHS, are members of PARTHENOS. Within PARTHENOS, specific activities have been set up to gather requirements (WP2) and implement solutions (WP4, WP5, WP6) to standardization and interoperability (e.g. Linked Open Data) issues.

1.4 Structure of the document

This document is organised in three central sections:

- Chapters 1-3 describe the scope, background, terminology and methods.
- Chapters 4-6 cover current use of standards and formats as well as interoperability issues.
- Chapters 7-10 provide recommendations, priorities for conversion services and conclusions.

¹ Data without Boundaries – DwB <http://www.dwbproject.org/>

² DASISH <https://dasish.eu/>

³ Introduction – ARIADNE Infrastructure <http://legacy.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/about-ariadne/introduction/>

⁴ ARIADNE Reference Model <http://legacy.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resources-2/ariadne-reference-model/>

⁵ PARTHENOS Project <http://parthenos-project.eu>

2. Terminology

2.1 Metadata

Metadata is often defined as “data about data”. Pomerantz (2015, p. 26) claims that this popular definition is not informative enough and provides an alternative definition “Metadata is a statement about a potentially informative object”. In the context of this deliverable, both these definitions are useful but too general. The purpose of metadata is to describe the data so that the data is understandable and usable, both now and in the future. And what is metadata from one perspective can be data from another, depending on the use and disciplinary traditions. This is why we find the definition by Bargmeyer and Gillman (2000) “Metadata is data that is used to describe other data, so the usage turns it into metadata” most appropriate.

There are many typologies used to define the metadata. One basic typology is to divide metadata between technical metadata and content describing metadata i.e. descriptive metadata. More fine-grained typologies categorize metadata into smaller categories e.g. process, administration, description, structural, or technical metadata (e.g. Kimball et al. 2008, p. 116-117). Beyond these different typologies of metadata, the underlying purpose of metadata remains the same.

In this deliverable we consider metadata as data that is used to describe, to give a meaning to other data so that we can take action on it. Depending on the structure and content of the data and metadata these actions may be human or machine mediated.⁶

2.2 Standard

Cambridge Dictionary (2019) defines the term “standard” as “a pattern or model that is generally accepted”. In this deliverable, the term “standard” is used and understood in this sense, i.e. broadly. When using the term “metadata standard(s)”, we do not refer only to official standards (for example, ISO standards) but are foremost interested in established data and metadata management procedures, formats and best practices (domain norms or schemas) that are actively used in the SSH communities (i.e. *de-facto* standards).

2.3 Data

Zins (2007) defines data as “sets of signs that represent empirical stimuli or perceptions”. Even if this definition is popular, it is quite abstract for the purposes of this deliverable. Leonelli (2015) takes a more practical approach, considering (research) data first and foremost, as a “material artefact”. Leonelli (*idem*) emphasizes that data are always bound up with the medium and format in which they are conveyed. On the other hand, she describes data as any object that 1) may be thought of as acting as an evidence for some

⁶ Note that in this deliverable, annotations are considered as data and not as metadata. Sometimes it might be unclear what is metadata and what is the annotation data. Uytvanck, Goosen and Windhouwer (2012, 2-3) present some practical advice for separating these two, e.g. annotation data contains elementary linguistic information. They also state that metadata describes the whole resource and not only a single sentence in a text corpus. Though annotations are used to describe other data, they do not fall into the category of metadata for the purposes of this paper.

phenomena and 2) is portable (possible to hand from one individual to another). A report by PARTHENOS remarks that research data is a specific type of data and by nature diverse (Hollander et al. 2017).

In this deliverable, we base our definition on Leonelli's (2015) work and define the term "data" as a medium and format dependent (material) artefact that is portable and may be used as evidence for some phenomena. However, we leave physical objects e.g. pot fragments outside of the discussion and concentrate on digital objects e.g. digital data matrices, videos, texts and photographs.

2.4 Data format

"Data format" is quite often interpreted only as a file format as indicated by a filename extension. However, the filename extension is not always sufficient for interpreting the data format. For example, for text annotations, XML is a common file format. You may open any XML file with a text editor, but if you want to use a text annotation XML file for analysis, you need a more sophisticated tool, specialized in that certain practise of text annotation. Therefore, each established practise of text annotation ought to be considered a data format, e.g. FoLiA⁷ and EAF⁸ need to be considered as "independent" data formats. Even though they are both using XML to represent the data, they represent the data following their own specification.

In this deliverable, "data format" is understood not only as a file format but also as established practices or standardized/specified ways of representing data.

2.5 Controlled vocabulary

Any prescribed set of terms used to limit the acceptable set of metadata values can be referred to as a vocabulary (Hider 2012, p. 251). The distinction between a vocabulary and a controlled vocabulary is that terms of controlled vocabulary are stored and maintained using agreed procedures. In a controlled vocabulary, terms are suitable for community practices and they are also precisely defined. In other words, controlled vocabularies are formally managed (Neiswender 2009). In this deliverable, "controlled vocabulary" means the formally managed collection of terms and their definitions that are used to describe an object, for example, the subject or coverage.

⁷ FoLiA – Format for Linguistic Annotation <https://proycon.github.io/fofia/>

⁸ ELAN Annotation Format EAF http://www.mpi.nl/tools/elan/EAF_Annotation_Format.pdf

3. Methods

In order to collect information on existing practices, selected experts from each domain were interviewed. Task partners, including experts from all SSHOC domains, were able to suggest potential informants who were familiar with data, metadata and interoperability issues. The final selection was based on the relevant expertise and availability of the informants. The potential informants were first contacted by email introducing the project and task, explaining the purpose of the information collection and describing the interview process. The invitation email also contained preliminary interview questions.

Of the 18 persons contacted, 16 participated in the interviews (see Appendices for the list of informants). The domains the informants represented included social sciences (CESSDA, ESS and SHARE), arts and humanities (DARIAH), language sciences (CLARIN) and heritage science (E-RIHS). Social sciences, language sciences and arts and humanities were nearly equally represented with four to five informants from each domain, while heritage science was under-represented with only two informants.

The informants were given the opportunity to answer the questions independently before the interview. The interview questionnaires were available to the respondents in a spreadsheet format online. The interviews were conducted virtually between 25 April and 23 May 2019. The length of a single interview varied from 30 to 90 minutes. The informants had the opportunity to review and edit their responses after the interviews.

In addition to the interviews, we conducted desk research to supplement the answers given by the informants.

4. Standards and formats in use

This section summarizes the answers to questions about metadata standards, data formats and controlled vocabularies used by our informants' organizations.

The SSHOC Description of Action mentions several metadata standards or formats: CIDOC-CRM, DDI, CMDI, Dublin Core, RDA recommendations, PARTHENOS entity model, SSHOCro, metadata model for the SSHOC marketplace, OpenAIRE, DataCite, CESSDA Product and Services Catalogue & EQB metadata, an NSD data model, RDF and PROV-O. This long list shows that the SSHOC metadata landscape is heterogeneous and evolving. In contrast, the Description of Action mentions no data formats but only data types and some statistical programs. This is not to suggest, however, that the SSHOC data landscape is any less heterogeneous than its metadata landscape, as will be demonstrated in this section.

4.1 Metadata standards

In the interviews, 19 metadata standards⁹ were explicitly mentioned as being used by at least one informant. One additional standard, DDI 4, is still in development but some informants intend to use it as soon as it is

⁹ DDI Codebook, DDI Lifecycle and DDI 4 are considered separate standards, as they have different scopes and they are often used in parallel rather than a newer version replacing an older one.

available. When asked to limit their evaluation to the two most important metadata standards, the informants still gave 11 different standards (see table 1).

Table 1. Used metadata standards/formats according to our informants.

Selected two most important	CIDOC-CRM CMDI (Component Metadata Infrastructure) DataCite DDI Codebook DDI Lifecycle DDI 4 (not yet used) DC (Dublin Core) EDM (Europeana Data Model) MODS (Metadata Object Description Schema) OLAC (Open Language Archives Community) TEI (Text Encoding Initiative)
Used, but not among the two most important	EAD (Encoded Archival Description) IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) METS (Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard) ODRL (Open Digital Rights Language) PREMIS (Preservation Metadata Implementation Strategies) QuDEx (Qualitative Data Exchange Format) FITS (File Information Toolset) DCDDM (DARIAH Collection Description Data Model) Organizational/local schema

There is a clear division between scientific domains with regard to the most important metadata standards:

- **Social Sciences / CESSDA, ESS, SHARE:** DDI Codebook, DDI Lifecycle, DataCite, Dublin Core
- **Art and humanities / DARIAH:** TEI, CIDOC-CRM, Dublin Core
- **Language science / CLARIN:** CMDI, TEI, Dublin Core, OLAC
- **Heritage science / E-RIHS:** EDM, Dublin Core

The only one mentioned by representatives of all domains is, not very surprisingly, Dublin Core, which is also named as one of the two (in some cases three) most important standards by seven informants.

Most of the ‘top two’ standards (see table 1) focus on specific purposes closely associated with their domain, which presumably goes a long way towards explaining the obvious division over domains. Exceptions are DataCite which, while having the specific goal of making data citable, is open to all kinds of data, and Dublin Core, which is not very specific but also not very verbose. Another exception of sorts is CMDI, which is not a typical metadata standard at all but rather a framework intended to express a vast number of different metadata profiles using a common language.

When asked to give pros and cons of the most important metadata standards, some informants talked about the pros and cons of their infrastructure rather than specific standards. Therefore, table 2 contains a few standards missing any pros and cons. A clear pattern is nevertheless obvious: standards need to be

expressive. Pros include “high level of detail”, “tailoring to local needs”, “extremely expressive”, “flexible” and “brings together resources from different contexts”, all of which are connected to expressiveness. This is further strengthened by Dublin Core being described as having the con of being “not specific enough”.

Table 2. Pros and cons of the most important metadata standards as stated by the informants.

Standard	Pros	Cons
CIDOC-CRM	extremely expressive	complex and hard to use
CMDI	flexible, supports tailoring to local needs, extremely expressive	proliferation of profiles; complex, requires a lot of work; difficult to deliver semantic interoperability; complex and hard to use
DataCite	-	-
DDI Codebook	“DDI is the common metadata standard of the future, for survey data, but also moving into other data types”, high level of detail, interoperability between data archives	“[DDI] wasn't designed for disseminating questionnaires, it is very complex”
DDI Lifecycle	very flexible, “DDI is the common metadata standard of the future, for survey data, but also moving into other data types”, high level of detail, interoperability between data archives	“DDI 3 too much describing the DLC [data life cycle] not sufficiently on archiving”; “[DDI] wasn't designed for disseminating questionnaires, it is very complex”
DDI 4	“DDI is the common metadata standard of the future, for survey data, but also moving into other data types”, high level of detail, interoperability between data archives	-
DC	simplicity, “very simple, well-known and at least partly interoperable between disciplines”, “consistency across systems”	often not specific enough, simplicity
EDM	brings together resources from different contexts	specificity may be too high for common users yet too low for specialists
MODS	-	-
OLAC	-	-
TEI	extremely expressive, “useful for anything with text”, wide adoption	complex and hard to use

Interestingly, Dublin Core is also praised for its simplicity, a feature which makes it stand out from all the others. While the expressiveness of most standards is viewed as necessary and useful, their high complexity, difficulty of use or a high workload involved is clearly perceived as the downside, as is obvious from the cons column in table 2.

It seems clear that complex and expressive standards are necessary and that they need to be subject/domain specific to some degree. But it is also clear that many informants appreciate being able to use the simple Dublin Core standard, which allows them to create metadata that are interoperable/consistent across systems and disciplines.

4.2 Data formats

When it comes to data formats, it is worth noting that both CLARIN and DARIAH representatives mention encountering a vast number of different data formats. Even within one project, there may be a hundred different formats (DARIAH/ÖAW). The data upon which we base this analysis only accounts for the ones explicitly mentioned by our informants, leading to an imbalance based upon the fact that one of the informants from CLARIN provided a very detailed list of formats, while several other informants gave very general answers along the lines of “audio and images”. This heterogeneity in answers reflects the complications around file formats/data formats discussed in chapter 2 (Terminology - Data format). Table 3 lists data formats selected most important by at least one informant, and data formats mentioned but not considered most important.

Table 3. Used data formats according to our informants.

Selected two most important	CHAT Container formats (tar zip) CSV (Comma Separated Values) FOLIA (Format for Linguistic Annotation) EAF (ELAN Annotation Format) SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) STATA TCF (Text Corpus Format) TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) TIFF (Tagged Image File Format)
Used, but not among the two most important	EXCEL EXMARaLDA JPEG SAS (Statistical Analysis System) Triple-S (Survey Interchange Standard) TSV (Tab-Separated Values)

The selection of the most important data formats is mainly dependent on the media types that are common within the organisation. Data matrices (numerical data) are the most common media type within the social sciences, and SPSS and STATA are the statistical analysis software packages most common among the users. Thus, formats used by these software packages are considered the most important data formats. For long-term preservation, other formats, mostly CSV or TSV, are used. Language sciences deal with a variety of media types, and as a result of this many different data formats as well. TEI and FOLIA are often used for text-based resources, CHAT for transcriptions of speech corpora, EAF for transcription of speech and video (multimedia corpora) and EXMARaLDA for multimodal interaction. Texts and images are common media types within the arts and humanities, and TEI, TIFF and JPEG are preferred data formats.

Table 4. Pros and cons of data formats according to our informants.

Data format	Pros	Cons
CHAT	-	-
Container formats (tar, zip)	simple, wide-spread usage	-
CSV	-	-
FOLIA	-	not necessarily backwards compatible
EAF	-	-
SPSS	widely used, can be used in R	file size causes problems, not open software
STATA	can be used in R	-
TCF	-	-
TEI	XML is well-structured and easy to learn and share	“TEI can be very different to each other, so a federated search over different TEI files is not really possible”, overhead of descriptive metadata, large files
TIFF	-	-

Few informants gave format-specific answers to the questions about the pros and cons of data formats (see table 4), with a fair number instead commenting on problems relating to data formats in general. For example, with well-established formats the user knows what can be expected, whereas new formats may be unpredictable. The large variety in used formats makes it necessary to use many different tools, which may cost both money and working time for training or trial and error. XML-based files tend to be verbose and thus large, leading to an array of problems. Proprietary formats and advances in technology mean that a lot of time needs to be spent on converting between formats.

It is difficult to draw any conclusions about the pros of data formats. The high adoption rate and compatibility with popular software seem to be two themes.

One thing that is clear is that what might be viewed as “the same” data kind/data format is often represented in several different file formats. This is especially obvious with data for statistical analysis where file formats include CSV, TSV, STATA, SPSS, Triple-S and SAS, but also with the representation of (annotated) text.

4.3 Controlled vocabularies

The informants were asked about the usage of controlled vocabularies in their organization. The following CVs were mentioned:

CESSDA - CESSDA Topic Classification, DDI Controlled Vocabularies, ELSST

CLARIN - CLARIN Concept Registry, CLAVAS, ISO 639-1 language list, local vocabularies

DARIAH - GND (Gemeinsame Normdatei), OpenGeoNames, TADIRAH, TGN (Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names)

E-RIHS - AAT (Art and Architecture Thesaurus), PICO Thesaurus, TGN, VIAF (Virtual Authority File)

ESS - DDI Controlled Vocabularies (subset), ESS' own self-defined CVs

This list is in no way exhaustive, nor does it necessarily contain the most important ones, if such exist. There are 23 DDI Controlled Vocabularies (DDI Alliance 2018a) and in addition to them, DDI also requires or encourages the use of numerous other standardized vocabularies, such as ISO standards for locations, languages and so on. The situation is similar for at least some of the other larger metadata standards, suggesting that in fact hundreds of CVs may be in use in these communities. Task 7.4 will attempt to identify important controlled vocabularies and integrate them into the SSHOC infrastructure by aligning them with the SSHOC Reference Ontology (T4.8).

5. Perceived interoperability problems

5.1 Metadata interoperability problems

Several informants mentioned that concepts or metadata fields are not always accurately and clearly defined, resulting in different interpretations of the definitions. This problem is intensified in some cases by diverging definitions for what is essentially the same field in different standards (the example mentioned was DDI and DataCite).

Another problem mentioned is the mapping of very rich library-based metadata formats with very complex structures and recursion in metadata elements to CMDI, which is by definition not an extremely rich language, forcing users to have a determined approach to describe things.

Problems can occur with older metadata records not using modern standards. Such problems are mentioned by several informants and have to do with both form and content. Examples include entries from old archives in legacy formats which need to be converted or mapped to newer formats, and heterogeneous date formats which need to be unified. Related to this is legacy material where locally made assumptions may be opaque to a global user community, e.g. the language of a material may often not be explicitly stated when it is the only expected language of a certain collection.

A problem common to the two large standards in the social sciences and language sciences, DDI and CDMI, is on account of their flexibility. They achieve flexibility by offering a very large set of concepts/elements/fields. The describer has the possibility of choosing a subset, thus creating a profile which includes what the use case calls for and excludes everything else. The trouble with this is that there may be very little overlap between two user-created profiles. This can result in metadata descriptions that are technically compatible in terms of validation, they may not be comparable in terms of content.

It was also mentioned that there are some small interoperability problems between the two DDI versions Codebook and Lifecycle, though these were not specified further.

In the collaboration between CLARIN and DARIAH, CMDI from CLARIN can be represented in the DARIAH schema registry and at least a fundamental interoperability can be assured using mappings defined in the DARIAH data modelling environment (DME).

5.2 Data interoperability problems

Responses across all the informants referenced some data interoperability problems. The most common problem was the limitation of some tools to a single data format, indicating a need for format conversion to enable the use of the full range of data management tools. Quality assurance is also an issue when a conversion process or tool accepts a data format but misinterprets the data structures or content. One example of this is with numerical data that includes decimal delimiters or thousand separators. The characters used as decimal delimiters and thousand separators vary, so in one tool “10,000” means ten and in another it means ten thousand.

There are many conversion tools, and the informants were very well aware of them. However, some informants raised an issue with conversions: the loss of information. Data formats have different levels of granularity or expressivity. If the conversion is made from data format with high granularity to data format with low granularity, a great deal of information disappears. In other words, the loss of information occurs when converting “rich” data format to “less rich” data format. It was also mentioned that when data formats are clearly meant to represent different data types (e.g. video and data matrices), interoperability problems are unavoidable.

Sometimes interoperability problems exist within the data format. Many data formats have version dependent features. Even if the filename extension remains the same, the newer version of data format may not be compatible with the older version.

Legacy data formats can present a particularly complex interoperability challenge. If the data format is ancient enough, there are no tools on modern computers that could either read the file properly or convert it into a modern file format. Even if a tool chain can be built to convert a legacy format up through multiple tools into a modern usable and preservable data format, this can be costly and each conversion step increases the risk to the data.

Data formats without proper documentation may also cause problems. One example of this is the lack of DTD/Schema documentation in data formats based on XML. In this case, without any formal documentation or the co-dependent schema file, it is impossible to know if the file is valid or not. Some interoperability issues were also found with versioning, 3D objects, scanned files and database alignment.

Some informants explained their reasons for not reporting interoperability problems. One reason was that some consortiums/organizations have comprehensive instructions or guidelines for selecting suitable data formats. Interoperability problems are avoided by following these instructions or guidelines closely. Another explanation for the low number of reported interoperability problems was that the

consortiums/organizations use one format for one purpose. On the other hand, some informants mentioned that there is such a wide variety of data formats that it is impossible to list all interoperability problems. What may further lead to interoperability issues is if the instructions and guidelines are not followed or if there are no instructions and guidelines in place.

As mentioned above, the informants did not report many interoperability problems. For the majority of them, it was clear that in many cases data formats are complementary by nature. If the formats are not interoperable, it is not an issue but rather an unavoidable consequence of their different natures. What the informants considered complicated were the interoperability problems between data formats designed for similar purposes and between different versions of the same format.

6. Interoperability landscape

Though the focus of this deliverable is on the identification and prioritisation of metadata and file format conversions and associated services in SSHOC, the concept of interoperability has broader implications. This section outlines some of the wider interoperability challenges.

As we seek to defragment our scientific practices and embrace common research infrastructures across multiple disciplines, the range of actors and systems that need to interoperate expands rapidly. This is particularly applicable at a time when archives and other data repositories are moving from mediating *access* to data (from discovery to download) to mediating *use* of the data: providing specialist analytical environments that can support the size, complexity and sensitivity of the data.

Needs and expectations will change as digital objects move through a range of custodians for different processes throughout the research data lifecycle. Availability of data in relevant formats, format compatibility and metadata compliant with relevant standards are essential but interoperating goes beyond them.

Even for the most specialist or technical challenges, the human factors are always critical. The relevant actors in an interoperability scenario must reach a shared understanding of the digital objects which are in scope. Rather than a technologist requiring that a researcher understands their SQL database or RDF graph, or the researcher handing the developer a complex dataset and demanding a great user interface, there needs to be some common ground. This involves defining the purpose and boundaries of the objects and the characteristics we need to work with.

The person and organisational issues for interoperability may go beyond a common understanding or the availability of a technical solution. Some data may not interoperate across national boundaries for legal reasons. Some data may not be linked and used to generate new objects for ethical reasons. Even where legal and ethical boundaries are addressed, organisations acting as data owners or data stewards may see ‘public opinion’ (with or without public understanding of the issues) as a reason not to undertake otherwise valuable work. Public sentiment around perceived mishandling of personal data is having operational consequences for the availability and level of openness of data and this poses an extension of the interoperability challenge. The final organisational challenge is maturity and whether the organisation has

the data management, technical or project maturity to meet the often-complex challenges of interoperability.

What are the relevant characteristics of the data that impact its use and therefore interoperability in a given environment? Size, sensitivity, structure, quality, source?

Data supported with standard metadata supports functionality, i.e. actions on the data which would not otherwise be possible. But as covered above, the boundary between data and metadata can be unclear and depend on the actors' perspectives. The original data collected or created may be held in a format that already supports rich metadata (such as DDI Lifecycle) or the digital objects may be supported by separate metadata objects (such as a DataCite-compliant XML file submitted during a DOI minting process). Successful interoperability depends on a common understanding of the required data and metadata characteristics, how they are instantiated as objects (including pre/post format conversion) and how they may change over time. But we know that in practice successful reuse of data for many purposes does not always require complete understanding of all interoperability aspects, nor is it always possible.

To support confidence in the data and metadata – across any changes – requires provenance information, clarifying the who, when and why behind the original data and the subsequent changes. This implies a need to understand the data structures and the application of identifiers to objects and parts of objects as well as any changes, including conversions. Data stewards may need to define the wider context of related objects and may need to be aware of which other copies or versions are 'out there'. For example, it may be important to a repository to know if it is the sole custodian of the only copy of a dataset, or one of many actors curating and providing access to those data.

It can also be important to differentiate between types of interoperability. Logical interoperability of classes of digital objects, e.g. tabulations with the same variables which support methodologically sound data linkage, is not always aligned with physical interoperability. Data files that are content-wise equivalent may not be interoperable if one is in SPSS and the other in Excel. Conversely, the physical interoperability of opening a csv file and an xlsx file in Excel does not guarantee the logical interoperability of the data they contain. It may also be important to differentiate between data and metadata that can interoperate at a technical level, and which may interoperate.

7. SSHOC recommended standards and formats

7.1 Recommended metadata standards

The SSHOC organisations use a wide variety of metadata standards. This reflects the fact that there is no single standard that can support all kinds of data and all use cases. Metadata standard selection criteria emphasize fitness for use – the first step should always be determining the needs the metadata needs to serve. (Bruce and Hillman 2004, Beall 2007, Zhu and Harris 2011, Data Without Boundaries 2014, DASISH 2014, Drude et al. 2016). In addition, the FAIR Principles provide guidance for those wishing to enhance the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of their data holdings (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

The analysis of the interviews confirmed that the requirements for the metadata are different in each domain and for different purposes. The data used in domains vary from numeric data matrices collected by surveys to annotated videos and 3D models of historical objects. When the data to be described by metadata are diverse, the metadata need to be diverse too. Also, the division between metadata and data is sometimes unclear - in some cases metadata may be used as data. Therefore, we recommend specific metadata standards to be used for each domain (see table 6) and two general metadata standards to be used by all domains especially for the needs of building conversion services: Dublin Core and DataCite. They both come with pros and cons.

The popularity of Dublin Core is due to its long history, familiarity and the fact that it is mandatory in the commonly used protocol for metadata harvesting, OAI-PMH (The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting 2015). According to interview results, OAI-PMH is used in every SSHOC domain, which implies that Dublin Core is used in every SSHOC domain. Dublin Core includes the basic metadata fields (e.g. title, subject, description, identifiers, rights) (Dublin Core Metadata Initiative: Creating Metadata 2019), so it is general enough to be suitable for different domains and for data discovery in aggregated metadata catalogues. Dublin Core has been mapped, for example, to CMDI (Zinn et. al 2016), DDI Codebook (DDI Alliance 2018b) and DDI Lifecycle (DDI Alliance 2017). Since Dublin Core is a general metadata standard, conversion from domain specific metadata standard to it leads almost always to loss of information. However, it is important to note that if the conversion from domain specific metadata standard to Dublin Core is done carefully, meaningful and informative documentation with Dublin Core is possible.

Two other metadata standards that could be recommended for all domains are the DataCite Metadata Schema (2019) and the OpenAIRE Application profile (OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives 2015). Both have shortcomings that make them less attractive, including the fact that their priority is for use within their own resource discovery systems. However, both have good documentation and clearly stated status (recommended, mandatory) information for each metadata field. It is important to note that OpenAIRE is based on DataCite, but there are few differences (OpenAIRE: Use of DataCite 2015). The DataCite Metadata Schema only accepts DOI as a persistent identifier (PID), whereas OpenAIRE also accepts ARK, Handle, PURL, URN and URL. OpenAIRE has more fields that are “mandatory if applicable” (MA) than DataCite, e.g. links to publications and datasets as well as the funding information. The reason for this is that OpenAIRE Catalogue only publishes metadata that has either OpenAIRE identified funder information or links to other resources (publications, datasets) published on OpenAIRE.

We recommend DataCite but with the relaxation of the rule of the accepted PID types so that ARK, Handle, PURL, URN and URL are acceptable in addition to DOI (as in OpenAIRE). We call this a “relaxed DataCite”. It is worth noting that this relaxed DataCite is not a valid DataCite if a PID other than DOI is used and therefore will not be compatible with systems based on DataCite.

Dublin Core and relaxed DataCite serve the basic requirements for different domains and we gain common terms which support the discovery and use of a wide range of digital objects on a relatively high level of granularity (study or collection level). However, we acknowledge the specialised concepts critical to in-depth work and, especially from the reusability viewpoint, they are both too general to be used as the only metadata standard, so more detailed domain-specific standards are needed as well.

As mentioned earlier, the metadata landscape is evolving. The standards or initiatives to be followed include schema.org¹⁰, RDA recommendations¹¹, the recently published DDI-based CESSDA Metadata Model (CMM)¹², and the unpublished E-RIHS SMM (Scientific Metadata Model, application profile of CIDOC). Based on the interviews, schema.org is currently used only by some SSHOC organisations, but some informants mentioned that it is under discussion. RDA’s metadata recommendations did not come up in the interviews as such, but two informants indicated that they are active in RDA. In addition, CESSDA and DANS are organisational members of RDA.

In order to get an overview of the actual level of use of the metadata standards, we gathered information on the number of existing metadata records in SSHOC communities. The results of this desk research are summarised in table 5.

¹⁰ Schema.org <https://schema.org/>

¹¹ RDA: Metadata IG <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/metadata-ig.html>

¹² CMM CESSDA Metadata Model <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3238175>

Table 5. Metadata records in SSHOC communities.

SSHOC community	Metadata standard	Number of records (rounded)	What is considered a record	Source of information
CESSDA	DDI	30 000	study / dataset	CESSDA data catalogue https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/ and the web pages of CESSDA Service Providers (SPs). $\frac{2}{3}$ are DDI Codebook records and $\frac{1}{3}$ are DDI Lifecycle records.
	DDI	5 000 000	variable	Calculated estimation based on the web pages of CESSDA SPs. $\frac{2}{3}$ are DDI Codebook records and $\frac{1}{3}$ are DDI Lifecycle records.
CLARIN	CMDI	1 014 000	all types of Language Resources which can be individual files or collections of files or databases	Clarín Virtual Language Observatory (https://vlo.clarin.eu). NOTE that this catalogue harvests metadata all over the world and converts several metadata formats to CMDI (Van Uytvanck et al. 2012)
DARIAH Isidore DARIAH-DE DARIAH-IT	Dublin Core Terms, SKOS, ORE; DARIAH Collection Description Data Model (DCDDM)	Isidore: 2 003 500 DARIAH-DE: 212 DARIAH-IT: 487	research data of various types (images, text, maps, multimedia, bibliographies, etc.); Collection	No central catalogue, rather national nodes: ISIDORE, search filtered with “scope: sources of research” . NOTE that Isidore harvests metadata all over the world DARIAH-DE Collection Registry https://colreg.de.dariah.eu/colreg-ui/collections/
E-RIHS	CIDOC-CRM	N/A	Multi-layered images Text file Mapping images Relational table Plotted data	ARCLAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB, DIGILAB access platforms (http://www.e-rihs.eu/access/)
	PARTHENOS Entities Model (PEM)	124 153	Dataset Physical Collection Service Software Actor Project Standard	PARTHENOS Joint Resources Registry: (https://ckan-parthenos.d4science.org)
ESS	DDI Codebook	8	study	ESS Data Nesstar http://nesstar.ess.nsd.uib.no/webview/ NOTE These are large multinational studies by European Social Survey (ESS) collected every two years since 2001

SHARE	DDI Lifecycle	16	study	http://www.share-project.org/data-documentation/share-data-releases.html and http://www.share-project.org/special-data-sets.html NOTE These are large multinational studies by Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe collected since 2004
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Based on the usage numbers in table 5 and corroborated by the answers to our question about the two most important standards (compare chapter 4.1), we recommend the metadata standards listed in table 6 for use within the SSHOC sub-communities. Dublin Core and/or DataCite are especially important because they can provide a bridge between the diverse domains, supporting metadata interoperability as well as data discovery - the F and I of the FAIR Principles. The domain-specific standards provide the refinement that is necessary to satisfy the needs within each domain (the R of the FAIR Principles). Most domain-specific standards are mapped or easily mappable to Dublin Core, suggesting a path towards easily attainable low-level interoperability without having to impose completely new systems or workflows on the communities.

Table 6. Recommended metadata standards.

Domain / ERIC	Recommended metadata standards
All	Dublin Core ¹³ , relaxed DataCite ¹⁴
Social Sciences / CESSDA, ESS, SHARE	DDI Codebook, DDI Lifecycle ¹⁵
Heritage Sciences / E-RIHS	CIDOC-CRM ¹⁶ (and its extensions, especially PEM ¹⁷)
Language Sciences / CLARIN	CMDI ¹⁸
Arts and Humanities / DARIAH	CIDOC-CRM (and its extensions), EDM ¹⁹ , TEI (teiHeader) ²⁰

The recommendation includes a limited number of currently used metadata formats. Repositories and organizations may need to use other formats more suitable for their specific use case(s). It is important to document the used standard(s) preferably in a machine-actionable way. It is also recommended to provide conversion into Dublin Core or/and relaxed DataCite to enable interoperability.

¹³ Dublin Core Specifications <http://dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/>

¹⁴ DataCite Schema <https://schema.datacite.org/>

¹⁵ DDI Specifications <https://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/>

¹⁶ CIDOC-CRM reference manual http://www.cidoc-crm.org/sites/default/files/Documents/cidoc_crm_version_5.0.4.html

¹⁷ PEM (PARTHENOS Entities Model) is a pivot format used in PARTHENOS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2668433>

¹⁸ CMDI <https://www.clarin.eu/content/component-metadata>

¹⁹ EDM <https://pro.europeana.eu/resources/standardization-tools/edm-documentation>

²⁰ TEI Guidelines <https://www.tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/index.html>

7.2 Recommended data formats

There are many different media types used in the field of heritage sciences, social sciences and humanities. Unlike file formats and metadata standards which are amenable to some degree of conversion, media types are not usually convertible to other media types without significant loss of information or distorted result. In table 7, we recommend some data formats for each media type. If possible, we recommend open formats instead of proprietary formats. The more open formats reduce the risk of only being supported by a limited number of applications. These formats have been chosen with a two-phase method. First, we examined the information reported in the interviews and particularly the answers to the question about the two most important data formats. Second, we supplemented this information with a list of preferred formats^{21 22 23 24} from different domains, if available.

Table 7. Recommended data formats.

Media type	Data format / file format
Data matrices (numeric)	CSV (Comma-Separated Values) + text file for additional information e.g. variable labels, SPSS portable
Images	tiff (Tagged Image File Format), jpeg (Joint Photographic Experts Group), svg (Scalable Vector Graphics)
Videos	mpeg (Moving Picture Experts Group), mp4 (MPEG-4 Part 14)
Audio	flac (Free Lossless Audio Codec), wav (Waveform Audio File Format)
Text	odt (Open Document Text), txt with utf-8 encoding
Annotations (Text)	TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) , TCF (Text Corpus Format), FoLiA (Format for Linguistic Annotation)
Annotations (Video)	EAF (EUDICO/ELAN Annotation Format)
Annotations (Audio/Speech)	CHAT (Codes for the Human Analysis of Transcripts); EXMARaLDA (EXtensible Markup Language for Discourse Annotation); TextGrid (annotation file format of the computer system Praat)
3D	x3d (eXtensible 3D Graphics)

²¹ Collection of CLARIN file formats <https://www.clarin.eu/content/standards-and-formats>
van het Meertens Instituut

<http://www.meertens.knaw.nl/cms/images/stories/data/PreferredFormatsMI.pdf>

²² ARCHE preferred and accepted formats (DARIAH)

<https://arche.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/browser/formats-filenames-and-metadata#formats>

²³ Social sciences (CESSDA)

<https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Expert-Guide/3.-Process/File-formats-and-data-conversion>

FSD <https://www.fsd.uta.fi/aineistonhallinta/en/data-formats-and-software.html>

UK Data Service <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/format/recommended-formats>

²⁴ PARTHENOS report on Standardization <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2607014>

In this phase of its evolution, E-RIHS is not yet in a position to recommend a specific format. Later in the process of building the DIGILAB, E-RIHS will be able to select and support specific formats.

The number of existing data or file formats for each media type is enormous. It is obvious that data or file formats other than the ones recommended here are also required. When using formats besides the ones recommended, one should follow the domain-specific best practices. If possible, use open formats to ensure application independent processing of files.

7.3 Recommended format for controlled vocabularies

Humans can understand the semantics of data and documents, but this is not the case for machines. Using common or compatible vocabularies increases interoperability between metadata standards and records. We asked the informants which standards or formats they use to encode controlled vocabularies, or in which formats they CVs are available. Nine informants mentioned SKOS. This included all respondents from CESSDA and CLARIN, one from DARIAH and one from E-RIHS, so SKOS is widely used in all SSHOC domains. Two informants did not respond and one mentioned that their work with CVs is currently manual.

Our recommendation for expressing vocabularies is thus the SKOS specification. It is a model and an RDF vocabulary for expressing the basic structure and content of concept schemes such as thesauri, classification schemes, subject heading lists and other types of controlled vocabularies (SKOS 2009).

8. Priorities for providing conversion services and planning solutions

While it is acknowledged that the ideal interoperability solution would be to use a single common metadata standard and data format, the reality is that diversity is essential for efficient research data management. There is also the matter of already existing procedures, software and expertise that makes it difficult for communities and organizations to switch to another metadata standard or data format suddenly. This does not mean that communities and organizations should not aim for standardization and limiting the number of schemas used. However, in the scope of SSHOC and this task we accept the existing diversity and aim at providing and pointing to conversion services for what we consider the major recommended metadata standards and data formats used in the SSH.

One of the goals for SSHOC task 3.5 is to provide an Interoperability Hub for the SSH, consisting at least partly of a portal with usable conversion services or advice and links to those. However, in view of the limited resources available for creating new conversion software and services, we need to come to a prioritization based on our understanding of the interoperability landscape. The discussion and the results of the interviews presented in this report have an important role in gaining this understanding.

Some interoperability solutions cannot be provided by a single software service but require more complex workflows. In such a case, a description and references to these workflows should be considered as a best effort solution. The SSHOC Marketplace to be built in SSHOC WP7 should register such complicated solutions. It is also useful to make a note of interoperability solutions identified by the stakeholder infrastructures that will prove beyond our capacity to provide. However, we must leave it to other initiatives to provide them.

With respect to the functionality of the Interoperability Hub, potential action lines within SSHOC (see table 8) could be to:

- provide guidance and references to a potential solution (G);
- link to a readily existing non-SSHOC software service (L); to be considered if the service is public and easy to use
- integrate existing software services in the Interoperability Hub, making it a SSHOC service; to be considered when the software is not available as a public service but can be provided relatively easily (e.g. conversion software currently embedded in existing tools) (I)
- develop a new service and integrate it in the Interoperability Hub (D)
- describe recommendations for new conversion solutions.

Table 8 shows an inventory of (meta)data format conversions we are aware of, through the interviews or otherwise, and potential conversions that would need to be provided by SSHOC. Conversions from very institution-specific formats are not included in the table.

Determining the priority of providing conversion services is done on a pragmatic basis:

- missing conversions with the highest demand
- existing software services for conversion that are easily integrated or duplicated are considered easy to achieve
- conversions for technical media formats for audio, images and video are considered a low priority, since they are not specific for the SSH and the informants do not mention this as a problem
- cross-community conversion services needed for SSHOC, e.g. task 3.3 where NLP processing needs to be performed on structured data from the Social Sciences

We expect that the prioritisation will change in the course of the project with the appearance of new requirements from other WPs (we will do a continuous scan).

Table 8. An analysis and summary from the interview responses.

Community	Challenge	Solution	SSHOC action & priority
CESSDA/ ESS/ SHARE	DDI version conversions	Sledgehammer, table with mappings	G
	DDI other metadata format conversions	DDI / DataCite / Triple-S conversion XSLTs	I
	Statistical package format conversions	Sledgehammer, Stat/Transfer, Python library, specific script	I, L (StatTransfer, Sledgehammer)
CLARIN	mainly linguistic annotation format conversions, some document and media conversion	several tool built-in conversions (ELAN, Praat, Weblicht, FoliaTools, PaQU, ...), Pandoc, OpenConvert, NLTK	I, L
	media conversion	ImageMagick	low
	ISO 24622-2 based metadata schemas/CMDI conversions	CMDI2RDF service, some special XSLTs for example for some CMDI profiles to Dublin Core, MARC 21, EAD, RDF, HTML (including Microdata according to schema.org)	I
DARIAH	metadata conversions	TEI to CMDI (OEAW), metadata crosswalks	I/L
	text format conversions	TEI-OxGarage to transform DOCX-Files to TEI XML	L
	structured data conversions	Karma for creating Linked Data	L
	image type conversions	IIF Image server	G, low
E-RIHS	metadata conversions	X3ML (Parthenos), different mappings to PEM the PARTHENOS CIDOC-CRM extension	L, low
SSHOC cross-community	structured data to text format conversion needed for SSHOC e.g. task 3.3	tbd.	I, high
	All service metadata to SSHOC Marketplace descriptions	tbd.	I, high

	semantic vocabulary alignments (mapping, cross-walks)		
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9. Discussion

This report provides an inventory of data and metadata formats that are currently used and relevant for the SSHOC communities, recommendations of specific formats for increasing interoperability, and prioritisations for providing conversion services and planning solutions. Our report takes a very pragmatic and SSHOC-centric approach to these complex issues.

The interview responses, limited as they are, provide a good insight into the world of metadata standards, data formats and interoperability issues in the various SSHOC domains. To get a more comprehensive list of interoperability challenges, a much wider sample would have been needed but was out of scope of this task. On the other hand, ideally, we would not require another round of interviews to identify this kind of information in the future. Instead, this could be solved by the generation of standard documentation from each community/infrastructure describing the digital objects/formats they manage and the supporting metadata/standards. A coordinated registry of standards and formats could be developed and managed at the SSH level. Initiatives for such registries have been taken before, e.g. in RDA context or as part of the research infrastructures themselves. Such existing efforts should be a basis for future work.

The interviews confirmed the findings from earlier projects that different communities are using different standards and formats because they have different needs. That said, the resources need to be described in an appropriate way in all domains so that the researchers are able to discover and use them. In addition, the tools and applications researchers use in different stages of data lifecycle and research workflow need to be able to communicate with each other. This means that interoperability is needed.

In this report, the focus is on the syntactic interoperability (common structures) of standards and formats. Semantic interoperability (common meaning) is out of the scope of this task. It is clear that using a specific metadata standard or data format does not guarantee good quality or transmission of meaning. For example, two well-formed DataCite records do not necessarily contain metadata of comparable scope or quality. Semantic interoperability can be achieved, for example, by using controlled vocabularies.

Our recommendations are based on the interviews and on the current usage of standards and formats, with a focus on the needs of the SSHOC project. It should be noted that organisations should select the metadata standard or data format that best fits their requirements. One of these requirements should be interoperability. There are other needs, such as support to ongoing access and long-term preservation, but they are not in focus here.

The interviews revealed some interoperability problems but perhaps fewer than expected, which might well be due to the limited number of interviews or the fact that organisations have adequate measures and processes in place to overcome the problems. One of the problems mentioned was lossy conversion from a rich domain-specific format to a more generic format. While true, it does not mean that lossy conversion is

completely without value. Again, it depends on the use case. For example, for discovery purposes, one may convert multiple highly specialized metadata records to one more generic one where specific information is lost, but what is left is unified or harmonized and can be used for discovery across heterogeneous resources. Similarly, for example in a Natural Language Processing (NLP) task, one could reduce a complex TEI document to simple text in order to be able to process it with an NLP tool. For this specific step, one would lose the information encoded in the TEI but gain new annotation as provided by the NLP tool.

The informants also mentioned problems with filename extensions. It is worth keeping in mind that a filename extension is not always sufficient for interpreting the data format. For example, there may be complex dependencies beneath a single “format” such as an XML file. XML has its own underlying specification²⁵ and must conform to a schema for validation purposes. Tools or systems may limit themselves to handling only a subset of an XML schema, creating a narrower interoperability domain such as through DDI profiles²⁶.

Proprietary formats may also result in interoperability problems due to their lack of transparency. For example, for photography, some guidance acknowledges the use of RAW files for archiving (though not preferentially over lossless TIFF or JPEG2000)²⁷, but poorly documented commercial ‘dialects’ of RAW may present a serious interoperability challenge²⁸.

Another kind of interoperability problem is related to versioning and occurs when conversion tools change or the structure of formats change. These could cause a previously working conversion process to break.

Many of these interoperability problems can be avoided with good documentation of tools, including conversion tools, to note any possible limitations so that the user can make informed decisions about conversion and the usability of the converted data as well as to avoid the risk of destructive data manipulation.

In the interviews, some informants mentioned that they avoid interoperability problems by following their own or their consortium’s guidance. While this is locally effective, it might have several corollaries especially if the local standards or formats are very limited. For example, the practice of format limitation may be causing a large quantity of potentially valuable data in non-compliant formats to be rejected. In addition, the move from local practice to increased cooperation (either through cross-disciplinary work or through the use of shared infrastructures such as SSHOC/EOSC) could deliver a wave of new interoperability challenges.

Standardisation of data formats and metadata standards is a key part of the solution to the wider complexities of the interoperability landscape, including human and organisational factors, shared digital object and metadata models, and appropriate levels of granularity. Format conversions provide a key foundation for an interoperable system. Addressing the challenges on file-to-file basis is a necessary start, but bulk transformations are needed to scale to European scientific needs.

²⁵ XML 1.0 <https://www.w3.org/TR/xml/>

²⁶ DDI Profiles <https://www.ddialliance.org/resources/ddi-profiles>

²⁷ Digital Preservation Coalition <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/technical-solutions-and-tools/file-formats-and-standards>

²⁸ OpenRAW <https://www.openraw.org/info/index.html>

10. Conclusion

SSHOC brings together different multidisciplinary communities, traditions and practices from ERICs and projects in the ESFRI Social and Cultural Innovation domain: CESSDA, ESS, SHARE, CLARIN, DARIAH and E-RIHS. The human sciences are represented extensively in this project and the diversity of the disciplines and SSHOC communities is shown explicitly. We try neither to contradict nor to hide the diversity of the SSHOC communities – instead we accept it. The SSHOC communities differ e.g. in data types, metadata standards and data formats. Each community has its own established traditions and customs that may cause interoperability issues with other communities.

In this deliverable, we make recommendations for the SSHOC. We recommend two metadata standards, Dublin Core and (relaxed) DataCite, for all the SSHOC communities to be used beside their own metadata standards as “metadata exchange formats”, as the lowest common denominator for all the disciplines. Because of the diversity of the SSHOC communities, we also recommend metadata standards for each community based on existing practices. The recommendations of the data formats are made by media types. Even if the SSHOC communities are different in nature, the media types are quite similar. The recommended data formats are a selected set of data formats used by the SSHOC communities. For the documentation of controlled vocabularies, SKOS is recommended. We also prioritize the conversion services to be implemented in the Task 3.5.

We hope that the recommendations and the planned conversion services may serve as a starting point for better interoperability. However, other metadata standards and data formats are still needed and used. It is worth noting that the basis for any standard/format interoperability solution are explicit and sufficient standard/format descriptions. In the case of metadata and annotation data, this means references of all elements and values to accepted semantic registries. Although most of the standards/formats already have made a start with this, the results of the interviews show that a great deal of work remains to be done in this regard. This is also one of the FAIR (I4) requirements we consider extremely useful. To sum up, many interoperability problems can be avoided if standards, formats, practices and tools are documented well and transparently.

Areas of possible future investigation and elaboration include standard and format registries, rights management, version management, and coherent mapping between the features of different standards and formats.

Beyond WP3, this document is relevant to WP4, WP5, WP7 and WP9. Ongoing discussion between the work packages and tasks is needed. Interoperability is a non-stop process, so the work must go on in both this SSHOC task and the surrounding world.

11. References

Bargmeyer, Bruce E. & Daniel W. Gillman (2000). Metadata Standards and Metadata Registries: An Overview. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/05d6/a22f0ea1da685166787ebed63a44b0ddeac8.pdf> [28.6.2019]

Beall, Jeffrey (2007). Discrete Criteria for Selecting and Comparing Metadata Schemes. Against the Grain: Vol. 19: Iss. 1, Article 7. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7771/2380-176X.5228> [28.06.2019]

Bruce, Thomas R. & Hillmann, Diane I. (2004). The Continuum of Metadata Quality: Defining, Expressing, Exploiting. In Metadata in Practice, D. Hillmann & E. Westbrooks, eds. <https://hdl.handle.net/1813/7895> [28.06.2019]

Cambridge Dictionary (2019). Standard. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/standard> [14.5.2019]

DASISH (2014). Deliverable: D5.2A & D5.2B: Part A: Metadata Quality Improvement and Part B: Portal Progress report. https://dasish.eu/publications/projectreports/DASISH-D5.2_AB_final_25nov-R.PDF [7.6.2019]

DataCite Metadata Schema (2019). <https://schema.datacite.org/> [5.6.2019]

Data Without Boundaries (2014). Integrated deliverable D7.2 - D7.3. Standards with future relevance for European Social Science data infrastructure. - Needs, Key Areas, Rules & Best Practices in Metadata Standard selection and usage. http://www.dwbproject.org/export/sites/default/about/public_deliverables/dwb_d7-2_7-3_future-metadata-standards-usage-selection_integrated-report.pdf [7.6.2019]

DDI Alliance (2015). DDI Timeline. <http://www.ddialliance.org/system/files/DDI%20Timeline%20With%20Foundational%20Events-For-Website.pdf> [7.6.2019]

DDI Alliance (2017). Relationship to other Standards. Dublin Core and MARC <https://ddi-lifecycle-3-2-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/otherstandards/dublincore.html> [7.6.2019]

DDI Alliance (2018a). Controlled Vocabularies - Overview Table of Latest Versions. <http://www.ddialliance.org/controlled-vocabularies> [18.6.2019]

DDI Alliance (2018b). Mapping to Dublin Core (DDI Version 2). <https://www.ddialliance.org/resources/ddi-profiles/dc> [28.06.2019]

Drude, Sebastian; Sara di Giorgio; Paola Ronzino; Petra Links; Annelies van Nispen; Karolien Verbrugge; Emiliano Degl'Innocenti; Jenny Oltersdorf; Juliane Stiller & Claus Spiecker (2016). PARTHENOS D2.1 Report on User Requirements. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2204560> [28.06.2019]

Dublin Core Metadata Initiative: Creating Metadata (2019).

http://dublincore.org/resources/userguide/creating_metadata/ [5.6.2019]

Hider, Philip (2012). Information Resource Description. London: Facet Publishing.

Hollander, Hella; Francesca Morselli; Femmy Admiraal; Anders Conrad; Thorsten Trippel; Douwe Zeldenrust; Paola Ronzino; Sara Di Giorgio; Antonio Davide Madonna & Mark Hedges (2017). PARTHENOS D3.1 Guidelines for Common Policies Implementation (1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2668392> [28.06.2019]

Kimball, Ralph; Margy Ross; Warren Thornthwaite; Joy Mundy & Bob Becker (2008): The Data warehouse Lifecycle Toolkit, Second Edition. Indianapolis, Indiana: Wiley publishing.

Leonelli, Sabina (2015). "What Counts as Scientific Data? A Relational Framework." Philosophy of science vol. 82, 5: 810-821. <https://doi.org/10.1086/684083> [28.06.2019]

Neiswender, Caryn (2009). What is a Controlled Vocabulary? In The MMI Guides: Navigating the World of Marine Metadata. http://uop.who.edu/techdocs/presentations/MMI_Guides.pdf [15.5.2019]

OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives (2015). <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/index.html> [5.6.2019]

OpenAIRE: Use of DataCite (2015). https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/use_of_datacite.html [5.6.2019]

Pomerantz, Jeffrey (2015). Metadata (MIT Press Essential Knowledge series). Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press.

SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System Reference (2009). W3C Recommendation 18 August 2009. <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/> [18.6.2019]

The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (2015). <https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html> [5.6.2019]

Van Uytvanck Dieter; Twan Goosen & Menzo Windhouwer (2012). CMDI and Granularity. https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/AP3-007-CMDI_and_granularity.pdf [17.6.2019]

Van Uytvanck Dieter; Herman Stehouwer & Lari Lampen. Semantic metadata mapping in practice: the Virtual Language Observatory. <http://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-001M-0000-000F-85F1-Bt> [4.6.2019]

Wilkinson, Mark D; Michel Dumontier; IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific Data vol. 3, Article number: 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18> [14.6.2019]

Zhu, Hongwei. & Harris Wu (2011). Quality of data standards: framework and illustration using XBRL taxonomy and instances. Electronic Markets (2011) 21: 129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-011-0060-4> [28.06.2019]

Zinn, Claus; Thorsten Trippel; Steve Kaminski & Emanuel Dima (2016). Crosswalking from CMDI to Dublin Core and MARC 21. Conference Paper. Tenth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2016). http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2016/pdf/543_Paper.pdf [7.6.2019]

Zins, Chaim (2007). Conceptual approaches for defining data, information, and knowledge. Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology vol. 58, 4: 479-493.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/asi.20508>

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Appendix 1: List of interviewed informants

Darren Bell, CESSDA / UK Data Service

Sharon Bolton, CESSDA / UK Data Service

Daan Broeder, CLARIN / Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences

Matej Ďurčo, DARIAH / Austrian Academy of Sciences

Stefan Funk, DARIAH-DE / Göttingen State and University Library

Sara Di Giorgio, E-RIHS / Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of Italian Libraries and for Bibliographic Information

Andreas Henrich, DARIAH / University of Bamberg

Tibor Kálmán, DARIAH-DE / Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG)

Maurice Martens, SHARE / CentERdata

Costanza Miliani, E-RIHS / National Research Council, Italy

Jan Odjik, CLARIAH

Knut Kalgraff Skjåk, ESS / Norwegian Centre for Research Data

Timo Steyer, DARIAH / Herzog August Bibliothek

Dieter van Uytvanck, CLARIN

Menzo Windhouwer, CLARIN / Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences

Wolfgang Zenk-Möltgen, CESSDA / GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences

Appendix 2: Interview questions

SSHOC Task 3.5 questionnaire on metadata standards, data formats and interoperability issues

Task 3.5 collects information on (meta)data standards and formats and interoperability problems by interviewing selected experts from each SSHOC domain. We are interested in the current practices within your infrastructure or consortium. The results will be included in report D3.1 that is due in June and used as a basis for further work on interoperability solution services.

Our report will include summaries and examples, your responses will not be published. List of the names of the informants will be included in the report.

Some definitions:

- In the questionnaire, the term “metadata standards” is used and understood broadly. When using the term “metadata standard(s)”, we do not refer only to official standards (for example, ISO standards) but are also interested in established metadata procedures and best practices (domain norms).
- By “controlled vocabularies”, we mean the managed collection of terms and their definitions that are used to describe for example the subject or coverage of the description object.
- By “data”, we mean a digital set of values of (research) subjects that your organisation / consortium has stewardship of.
- Interoperability should be understood as laid out in the FAIR principles.
- By “collaborators / partners”, we refer to collaborators outside your own organisation or research infrastructure.

Thank you for your participation!

BACKGROUND INFORMATION OF THE INFORMANT

1.1 Name

1.2 Research Infrastructure / Organization

1.3 Areas of expertise

PARTICIPATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF METADATA STANDARDS AND DATA FORMATS

2 Are you involved in the management or development of any metadata standards, data formats or controlled vocabularies?

IF NO, continue to question 3.

2.1 Which metadata standards / data formats / controlled vocabularies? Please describe your involvement.

METADATA PRACTICES

3 Is your organization/consortium using any metadata standards (e.g. Dublin Core, ISO 24622-1/24633-2 (CMDI), CIDOC-CRM or DDI) or established procedures / best practices for metadata? At this point, we’re only interested in primary use. Conversions of your metadata (e.g. for harvesting purposes) will be asked about later.

IF NO, continue to question 4.

3.1 Which metadata standards / established procedures / best practices are used?

IF THE INFORMANT MENTIONS ONLY ONE, continue to question 3.1.2

3.1.1 Please select the two most important metadata standards your organization/consortium uses and describe why they are important.

3.1.2 How strictly does your organization/consortium follow the specifications of the metadata standards used? Do you, for example, have a local versions / interpretations / schema of a more formal standard? If yes, why?

3.2 What kind of objects does your organization/consortium describe using the metadata standard? Please describe a typical object and a typical metadata record. Thinking about the metadata standards your consortium/organization uses, how many records are there in each metadata standard?

3.3 What are the pros and cons of the metadata standards used in your organization/consortium?

IF USING ONLY ONE METADATA STANDARD, continue to question 3.5

3.4 Have you noticed any interoperability problems between the metadata standards used within your organization/consortium?

3.5 Are your collaborators/partners using the same metadata standards as your organization/consortium?

IF YES, continue to question 4.

3.5.1 Which metadata standards do your collaborators/partners use?

3.5.2 Have you noticed any interoperability problems between the metadata standards used in your organization/consortium and the metadata standards your collaborators/partners use? Please describe the problems.

IF THERE ARE NO PROBLEMS, continue to question 4.

3.6 Have you / your organization / your collaborator found any solutions for metadata interoperability problems? Please describe the solutions.

4 Which persistent identifier schema(s) does your organization/consortium use and for which kind of objects (persons, data, publications...)?

5 What is your vision of the future of the metadata in your organization/consortium e.g. which metadata standards will you be using ten years from today?

DATA FORMATS

6 Which data formats are used in your organization/consortium?

IF MENTIONS ONLY ONE, continue to question 6.2

6.1 Please select the two most important data formats your organization/consortium uses and describe why they are important.

6.2 Thinking about the data formats your organization/consortium uses, how many data files are there in each format? Please describe the extent of a typical data file (e.g. one variable in one data file or hundreds of variables in one data file)

6.3 What are the pros and cons of the data formats used in your organization/consortium?

IF USING ONLY ONE DATA FORMAT, continue to question 6.5

6.4 Have you noticed any interoperability problems between the data formats used within your organization/consortium?

6.5 Are your collaborators/partners using the same data formats as your organization/consortium?

IF YES, continue to question 7.

6.5.1 Which data formats do your collaborators/partners use?

6.5.2 Have you noticed any interoperability problems between the data formats used in your organization/consortium and the data formats your collaborators/partners use? Please describe the problems.

6.6 Have you / your organization / your collaborator found any solutions for data interoperability problems? Please describe the solutions.

7 What is your vision of the future of the data in your consortium/organization e.g. which data formats will you be using ten years from today?

EXPORT, CONVERSIONS AND HARVESTING

8 Does your organization/consortium use any conversion tools between data formats? Which tools and between which formats?

9 Does your organization/consortium use any conversion tools between metadata standards e.g. for exporting the primary metadata into other formats? Which tools and between which standards?

10 What measures does your organization/consortium take to ensure interoperability of the metadata standards you primarily use with other metadata standards?

11 Does your organization/consortium share metadata publicly? If yes, which protocols or tools are used for metadata sharing? (Provide link)

12 Does your organization/consortium provide metadata interfaces for commercial search engines, e.g. Google, Google Scholar or Schema.org microformats?

CONTROLLED VOCABULARIES

13 Which controlled vocabularies are used in your organization/consortium?

IF NOT USING ANY CONTROLLED VOCABULARIES, the interview is finished.

13.1 Are the controlled vocabularies formally managed? By who? Are they machine actionable or are there APIs available?

13.2 In which languages are these controlled vocabularies (the terms and their definitions) available?

13.3 Are the controlled vocabularies domain/discipline specific?

13.4 Which standards or formats are used for the documentation of the controlled vocabularies (e.g. SKOS)?